

STATIC AND DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF A NOVEL ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE FOAM CONCEPT FOR PROTECTIVE HELMETS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new anisotropic material concept namely composite foam is proposed as an alternative to next generation helmet liners which can potentially reduce head rotational accelerations. The Layered Composite foam concept comprises of foam layers with different densities which are glued to each other in a parallel or series configuration. Initial experiments such as static combined shear-compression and linear impact tests have been performed. The performance of composite foams has been compared with a commercial expanded polystyrene bead foam (EPS), with nominal density of 80 kg/m³, which is currently the most used material for bicycle helmets. In this study the two types of composite foam with parallel and series configuration have been produced. Combined shear compression results indicate the parallel configuration is more suitable in terms of shear-compressive properties as well as energy absorption. Moreover, linear impact results indicate that the composite foam concept can mitigate peak forces compared to a standard EPS foam.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric foams are extensively used in applications such as packaging, cushions, light weight sandwich structures, and thermal-acoustic insulation. Their high energy absorption capability makes them an excellent choice in designing protective helmets and crashworthy vehicle structures to reduce severe head injuries during collisions. Therefore, investigation of foam behaviour under both quasi-static and dynamic loading is of great importance.

On the other hand, in-service loading conditions are often multi-axial due to the complex geometries involved and uncertainty of the impact direction. To be specific, in a traffic accident a cyclist is prone

to oblique impact which is a combination of shear and compression loading. Shear and compressive forces are corresponding to angular and linear decelerations during collision, respectively. Angular acceleration is correlated with serious traumatic brain injuries such as acute subdural (ASDH) hematoma and Diffuse Axonal Injury (DAI) and thus should be minimized [1-5].

Conventional bicycle helmets consist of three layers: a thermoplastic outer shell, an expanded polystyrene foam (EPS) liner, and an inner layer of comfort foam padding. This design is intended to mitigate skull fracture and focal brain injury. Although the standard bicycle helmets protect cyclists against linear acceleration, their level of protection against angular acceleration could be improved [6-7].

In previous research in our multidisciplinary research group, it was proposed that by using highly anisotropic foam liner the tangential forces transmitted to the skull-brain system can be reduced, thereby reducing rotational acceleration. Prototype helmets using highly anisotropic polyethersulfone foam (PES) with highly elongated cells have been produced and tested using the oblique impact test rig at the KTH laboratories in Stockholm. The results indicated significant decrease in both linear and rotational acceleration [8]. However, anisotropic PES foam can only be produced in the form of flat slabs and cannot be thermoformed into the intricate geometry of a helmet. This is a significant drawback which hinders the use of this foam in commercial helmets. Another drawback is the price which makes this an economically not viable substitute for standard cheap EPS liners.

In this paper, a new material concept namely "composite foam" is proposed which consists of a parallel array of foam sheets with different densities, glued together, creating anisotropy at the macro level. The idea is to create mechanical anisotropy by combining different layers of isotropic foams. The advantage of this method is that the anisotropy ratio can be controlled by adjusting the mechanical properties and volume fraction of each constituent, very much like the use of fibres in a composite. Moreover, shaping the composite foam to the complex shape of a helmet is feasible.

2 HYPOTHESIS AND INITIAL RESULTS

Within our research team, it is proposed that by using highly anisotropic foam liner instead of conventional isotropic EPS foam, the tangential forces transmitted to the skull-brain system can be reduced. This can subsequently lead to mitigation of the rotational acceleration. A patent protecting the use of anisotropic foam in bicycle helmets was previously filed (Depreitere et al. 2008). To confirm the hypothesis, prototype helmets using highly anisotropic polyethersulfone foams were produced and tested and compared to a commercial children's helmet. Rotational impact tests were performed using the rotational impact test rig of KTH in Stockholm. A hybrid III dummy head was used in these experiments. In this rotational impact test set-up, a helmeted dummy head is dropped onto a moving sled mimicking an oblique impact condition. Comparative results of prototype helmets using highly anisotropic PES foam and standard isotropic helmets made of expanded polystyrene (EPS) foam are shown in fig.2. As observed, both linear (translational) and rotational accelerations were reduced significantly by using the anisotropic foam.

Figure 1. Schematic of MIPS rotational impact set-up; a head falling on a shooting sled.

Figure 2. Resultant translational (a), and rotational (b) accelerations versus time under oblique impact for standard helmets (isotropic EPS) and prototype helmets (anisotropic PES).

In this paper, a composite foam liner is proposed for the next generation of bicycle helmets which should lead to linear and angular acceleration mitigation. The idea is to create mechanical anisotropy at “macro level” as an alternative to the “micro level” anisotropy at cell level (foam with elongated cells). Therefore, inspired by the mechanics of (fibre-reinforced) composites, parallel and series configurations (see fig.1) have been made from foam with different densities. The advantage of composite foam is that the ratio of mechanical anisotropy can be adjusted by changing the properties and volume fraction of the constituents ($R \sim K_L/K_T$).

Figure 3. Schematic of composite foams in series and parallel configurations, with respectively transverse stiffness K_T and longitudinal stiffness K_L .

3 MATERIALS

In this paper, two different composite foams have been studied. The first composite foam is a combination of EPS foams with two different densities of 100 and 40 kg/m³ in both parallel and series configurations (see fig 4). The second composite foam is a combination of EPS 100 and a soft flexible polyurethane foam. PU foam was sourced from Huntsman and has a density of 150 kg/m³. This composite was also produced in two different configurations (parallel and series). In the two different

composites the volume fraction ratio of EPS40/EPS100 and PUF/EPS100 were both chosen around 33/67. Different foam pieces were glued together using Araldite epoxy glue.

Figure 4. Composite foam consisting of EPS 100 and EPS 40, in series and parallel configurations.

4 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The composite foams were tested under quasi-static combined shear and compression loading using a shear-compression set-up. Combined shear-compression loading is mimicking an oblique loading condition which is the case in a traffic accident.

Linear impact properties of the composite foams were measured using a drop weight impact set-up with a flat projectile. The peak forces can be related to linear accelerations.

4.1. Biaxial shear-compression set-up and test method

The test apparatus for this study was developed as an insert into an existing biaxial test bench for textiles. This insert device allows for the testing of foams by the application of compression displacements along one machine axis and the application of shear displacements along the orthogonal axis. The design of the apparatus is such that two blocks of foam are glued to 3 steel sample frames (fig. 5). Each axis has an independent displacement actuator and an independent load cell. The displacement rate of each axis can be varied from 0 to 20 mm/min meaning that mimicking any resultant angle of deformation, from pure compression (angle 0°) to simple shear (angle 90°), is possible. In this study all the samples were tested under a deformation angle of 45° , meaning both displacement rates along the shear and compressive axes were set to 2mm/min. Tests were performed at room temperature. Samples were cut into cubes of 5cm x 5cm x 2.5 cm.

Figure 5. Representative illustration of biaxial shear-compression test set-up.

The output of these tests consists of two simultaneous curves: a compressive stress-strain curve and a shear stress-strain curve.

4.2 Linear Impact

Linear impact experiments were done using a drop weight impact set-up with a flat aluminum tub (diameter 5 cm). Flat foam samples were placed on a steel bench as seen in fig.6. Total weight of the falling frame and height were set to 2.37 kg and 0.85m respectively. This leads to a total initial energy of 20 J. Force and displacement of the impactor projectile were monitored during the impact event; displacement was monitored with a laser sensor. Forces were measured using a load cell.

Figure 6. Drop weight impact set-up.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Combined Shear-compression test

The stress-strain response for EPS100.40.100 composite foam under a deformation angle of 45° is shown in fig.7 a for the shear and compression components separately. Both the behaviour of the series and parallel arrangements are shown. It is assumed that the ideal configuration is the one which can absorb a similar amount of energy compared with standard liner but at the same time shows lower shear stress levels. It is known that shear stresses are related to rotational deceleration and the goal is to minimize this. Simultaneously, the ideal configuration should have comparable compression stress levels to standard helmet liner to be able to withstand and absorb energy in linear impact.

As observed in fig 7a, the series assembly shows two plateau levels in the compression stress-strain curve. The first plateau is reached when the yield strength of the weaker foam is exceeded. In the first plateau, the weaker foam is compressed until it densifies. At that moment, the stress increases until the yield strength of the stronger foam is reached. The second plateau corresponds to the crushing of the stronger foam. In a parallel configuration, the stiffer and stronger foam dominates the behavior; higher yield strength is found, followed by a plateau ending by stress upturn due to densification. It is clear that the parallel configuration dissipates more overall energy which is considered as the area under shear and compressive curves up to densification. Therefore, parallel configuration seems more interesting for head protection, provided that the peak stress at yielding does not cause too high peak accelerations during impact. The shear stress strain curves of both configurations do not differ significantly, the differences are related to the compaction of the foam due to the compression stresses.

Fig 7.b compares the shear-compressive curves of the composite foam in parallel configuration and EPS 80 (which is the standard material used in commercial helmet liners); please note that the global densities of the systems are the same. As observed, the total energy is approximately the same for the composite foam and EPS 80, however, the shear stress levels in the composite foam are lower. Care should be taken that an oblique impact is a dynamic event and here the preliminary biaxial tests are performed in quasi-static mode. It is assumed that in a dynamic test the effect of anisotropy on shear behavior will be more pronounced.

From these first tests on composite foam with the two different configurations, it is apparent that the parallel configuration is more favourable than series configuration because of higher energy absorption capability. Moreover, it can be observed that parallel configuration is comparable to EPS80 in terms of energy dissipation. However, shear stress levels are slightly lower in parallel configuration.

Figure 7. Combined shear-compression test at deformation angle θ of 45° ; a) comparative graphs of composite foam (EPS100.40.100) with parallel and series configurations, b) comparative shear-compression graphs of composite foam in parallel configuration and EPS80.

Figure 9. Comparative shear-compression graphs of EPS80.PU.EPS80 composite foam in parallel configuration and EPS80.

Fig.8. shows a comparison of shear-compression graphs of the EPS80.PU.EPS80 composite in parallel configuration, with EPS80. The PU foam is a soft foam which has low compressive and shear properties. The PU foam plays the role of a soft interlayer which facilitates shear deformations. As observed in fig.8., incorporating the soft PU interlayer into the composite in parallel configuration leads to a significant decrease in shear stresses whilst the compressive stresses are comparable with EPS 80. These initial biaxial experiments give the first indication that composite foams have the potential to reduce shear forces, while simultaneously reducing the helmet weight if a low density soft foam is used.

5.2. Linear Impact

Initial impact experiments were done on flat foam samples using a drop weight impact. The impact peak forces can be correlated to linear acceleration. Fig.9b. shows a decrease in linear peak forces in EPS 100.40.100 (parallel) composite foam compared to standard EPS 80. The reduction in peak force is more significant in composite EPS80.PU.EPS80 (parallel) as shown in fig.9a. Moreover, peak force reduction is accompanied by prolongation of the impact duration, meaning that the deceleration is spread out in time, which in some conditions can be favourable to prevent injury.

Figure 9. Drop weight impact results for composite foams, as compared to isotropic EPS80; a) EPS80.PU.EPS80 tested in parallel versus EPS 80, b) EPS100.40.100 tested in parallel versus EPS80.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, by proposing a novel composite foam concept, anisotropy in foam behaviour at macro level was created. A composite foam consists of layers of foam with different densities glued to each other. These different layers can be glued to each other in parallel or series configuration. It is hypothesized that using anisotropic material for a helmet liner can lead to rotational acceleration mitigation by decreasing the shear stresses experienced by the head. Preliminary experiments such as a combined shear-compression test in quasi static mode and linear impact tests have been performed. Results indicate that the parallel configuration is more suitable in terms of overall mechanical behaviour and energy absorption. Also, linear impact results suggest that the composite foam concept could lead to peak force reduction compared with a standard helmet liner (EPS80 foam).

REFERENCES

1. A.H.S. Holbourn, Mechanics of head injuries, *Lancet* **ii**, 1943, pp. 438-441.
2. T.A. Gennarelli, A.K. Ommaya, L.E. Thibault, Comparison of translational and rotational head motions in experimental cerebral concussion. Proc. 15th Stapp Car Crash Conference, SAE P, **39**, 1971, pp. 797-803.
3. T.A. Gennarelli, L.E. Thibault, J.H. Adams, D.I. Graham, C.J. Thompson, R.P. Marcincin, Diffuse axonal injury and traumatic coma in the primate. *American Academy of Neurology*, **12**, 1982, pp.564-574.
4. T.A. Gennarelli, L.E. Thibault, Biomechanics of acute subdural hematoma. *Journal of Trauma*, **22**, 1982, pp. 680-686.
5. T.A., Mattei, B.J. Bond, C.R. Goulart, C.A. Sloffer, M.J. Morris, J.J. Lin, Performance analysis of the protective effects of bicycle helmets during impact and crush tests in pediatric skull models, *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*, **10**, 2012, pp. 1–8.
6. I.S Scher, E.M. Hardley, D. Richards, R. Thomas, Likelihood of brain injury in motorcycle accidents: A comparison of novelty and DOT-approved helmets. SAE Technical Paper, 2009, pp. 01–0248.
7. Y. Mosleh, K. Vanden Bosche, J. Vander Sloten, I. Verpoest, J. Ivens, Combined shear-compression test to characterize foams under oblique loading for bicycle helmets, Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Composites Materials ECCM16, Seville, Spain, June 22-26, 2014.